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POTENTIAL ANTITUBERCULAR AND SAR STUDY OF SUBSTITUTED [2-(1-BENZOFURAN-2-YL) QUINOLIN-4-YL] METHANOL AND [2-(1-FURAN-2-YL) QUINOLIN-4-YL] METHANOL ANALOGUES

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ABSTRACT

Indicating the importance of coupled heterocycles and their important role in the multitude progress of the diseases. In view of this, a series of [2-(1-benzofuran-2-yl) quinolin-4-yl] methanol and [2-(1-furan-2-yl) quinolin-4-yl] methanol (4a-c, 5a-c and 10a-f) were evaluated for their antitubercular activity against H37Rv strain by microplate alamar blue assay (MABA) method. The results revealed that compounds 4a and 5b-c exhibited excellent antitubercular potential at concentration of 1.6 µg/ml. The compounds 4b-c and 10a-c exhibited good activity at 6.25 µg/ml and compounds 5a, 10d and 10f showed significant activity at 12.5 µg/ml when compared with standard drugs pyrazinamide, streptomycin and ciprofloxacin. Furan and benzofuran coupled quinoline moieties are essential for activity as they possess excellent drug like characteristics, suggesting to be potentially best inhibitor of H37Rv strain.

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INTRODUCTION

Tuberculosis (TB) is an infectious disease caused by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (M.tb); it is the world's one of common cause of death [1]. Approximate 1.4 million people died in 2015 and more than 6.1 million are getting infected [2]. The present therapy is directly observed treatment short-course (DOTS) and DOTS-Plus (DOTS plus Second-line TB drugs) for Tb and resistant-TB [3, 4]. The TB has been spreading at a steady rate over the last decade [5] and the recovery in TB is alarming due to the development of pathogenic synergy with HIV. In the current treatment, the emergence of multi drug resistant TB (MDR-TB) and extensively drug resistant TB (XDR-TB) as a consequence of lengthy treatment, makes patient compliance difficult [6]. These problems are encouraged for the development of new anti-TB drug.

Furans are important structural entity in many medicinal products [7, 8]. Furan derivatives are known to show antioxidant [9], antibacterial [10], antifungal [11], antiviral [12] and nematocidal activity [13]. In fact, therapeutic agents containing furan have stimulated researchers in pharmaceutical chemistry all over the world [14]. Similarly benzofuran derivatives constitute a major group of biologically active heterocycles [15, 16]. Prominently, benzofuran ring systems bearing various substituents at C-2 position are widely distributed in nature [17] and have been reported to have antimicrobial, antibacterial, antifungal, antiviral and antioxidant activities [17, 18]. On the other hand, the quinoline ring system is one of the most essential structural fragments of a large number of natural and synthetic compounds displaying various biological activities such as antimalarial, antibacterial, antiasthmatic, antihypertensive and antiinflammatory [19-22]. Therefore, quinoline and its derivatives have found many applications in pharmaceuticals, as well as being synthetic building blocks for many compounds [23-26].

The molecular hybridization is a rational approach to design new prototypes after coupling different pharmacophoric subunits that can be recognized by two or more biologic receptors [27]. These strategies have been used in drug discovery to increase the efficacy. Encouraged by these observations, as a part of our research program, we have aimed at emerging a new biologically active heterocycles containing furan, benzofuran and quinoline moieties.

In view of these observations, and in continuation of our work on drug discovery through coupled oxygen and nitrogen heterocycles [28-31], furan, benzofuran, quinoline carboxylates and methanol moieties were coupled and considered to evaluate their *in vitro* antitubercular potential of the compounds reported earlier from our laboratory [32] and explored for their *in vitro* antitubercular activity.

METHODOLOGY

Antitubercular activity

The antitubercular screening of the molecules was carried on M.tb H37Rv strain, by microplate alamar blue assay (MABA) method [33]. Take sterile 96 well plates and add 200 μ l of sterile deionized water to outer perimeter walls for avoid evaporation of medium in test wells during incubation. Added the 100 μ l of the Middle brook 7H9 broth to 96 well plates and serial dilutions of the tested compounds and drugs, incubated at 37 °C for five days. After completion of incubation, 25 μ l of freshly prepared 1:1 ration of 10 % Tween-80 and almar blue reagent was added to the plate and further incubated for 24 hrs. After 24 hrs. change the colour was observed and the concentrations of the compounds inhibited were recorded. The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) is the lowest drug concentration that stopped a colour change from blue (no growth) to pink (growth). The drugs pyrazinamide, ciprofloxacin and streptomycin were used as positive standard for comparison.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In vitro antitubercular activity

The substituted derivatives (4a-c, 5a-c, and 10a-f) showed antitubercular activity with MIC value ranging from 1.6 to 12.5 μ g/ml and the results are reported in Table-1.

Table-1: MIC values of antitubercular activity against H37Rv strain.

Samples code	MIC μ g/ml
4a	1.6
4b	6.25
4c	6.25
5a	12.5
5b	1.6
5c	1.6
10a	6.25
10b	6.25
10c	6.25
10d	12.5
10e	50.0
10f	12.5

Note

Strain used: *M. tuberculosis* (H37Rv strain)

Standard drugs

Pyrazinamide- 3.125 µg/ml, Streptomycin- 6.25 µg/ml and Ciprofloxacin- 3.125 µg/ml

Among the tested compounds, 4a and 5b-c showed excellent activity with a MIC value 1.6 µg/ml, which showed good activity as compared with standard drugs. While the molecules such as 4b-c and 10a-c exhibited activity with a MIC value 6.25 µg/ml, and the molecules 5a, 10d and 10f display activity with a MIC value 12.5 µg/ml, which showed moderate activity as compared with standard drugs. Overall, the series of molecules were found to be possessing very good activity and prompt for further in depth investigation.

Structural activity relationship study

The few key features regarding structural requirements for these furan, benzofuran and quinoline methanol hybrids (4a-c, 5a-c and 10a-f) to exert their antitubercular activity was determined. Our strategy was to identify the key sub unit required for activity such as, either furan (influencing both antimicrobial and antibiotic properties of drugs) benzofuran (influence both the antimicrobial and antibiotic properties of drugs) [34, 35], quinoline (antimalarial and antitubercular agents) [36, 37], quinoline carboxylate and methanol (active pharmacophore, which allows its derivatives to readily interact with diversity of enzymes, receptors in organisms and acts as a prodrug) [36, 37]. Further, essential substituent's like, -Cl, and -F (electron withdrawing) groups varied at 6th and 8th position on quinoline ring to enhance their lipophilicity properties is studied. The compounds (4a and 5b-c) benzofuran coupled with quinoline carboxylate and methanol, these heterocyclic rings are essential in exhibiting better antitubercular activity; this might be because of lipophilic nature; of halogen substituted quinoline.

Antimicrobial, antibiotic properties and ring fusion is also acts as hydrophobic in nature [35]

Antimalarial and other broad spectrum biological activities [36, 37]

(4a)

Antimicrobial, antibiotic properties and ring fusion is also acts as hydrophobic in nature [35]

Antimalarial and other broad spectrum biological activities [36, 37]

(5b-c)

The methyl substituted furan coupled quinoline methanol (10d-f) showed less significant compare to the unsubstituted furan (10a-c); this might be because of methyl substituted molecule behaves as more lipophilic and it unable cross the hydrophilic layer of cell membrane.

Influencing on both antimicrobial and antibiotic properties [35]

Antimalarial and other broad spectrum biological activities [36, 37]

(10a-c)

The results demonstrated the following assumptions about the structural activity relationship it is evident, that halogen substituents on quinoline ring influencing the antitubercular activity and was found to be most active. The antitubercular potential of these compounds may be due to the ability to penetrate the lipid membrane of the mycobacterial cell, there by weakening the integrity of the cell membrane and allowing the cellular component to drain and subsequently cell death. Whereas bromo substituted derivatives found to be less active compared to the other derivatives, indicating the influence size of the group which determine the logP value. The introduction of electron withdrawing groups namely the chloro and fluoro groups has greater influence in the bioactivity of the compounds. Hence, over all the influence of esters, methanols and as well as electron withdrawing groups has recommended their importance to be an active leads for further study.

CONCLUSION

The present investigation indicated that the furan, benzofuran, quinoline carboxylates and methanols were found to possess good antitubercular activity (4a and 5b-c). The potent quinoline methanols will be further taken up for in-depth study by varying the functionalities on the aromatic rings with various electron withdrawing and electron donating groups, which were reference to the commercially available antitubercular drugs. Further examination is required for modification of lead to increase the antitubercular potency. The results indicate that the core moieties furan, benzofuran, quinoline carboxylates and methanols are essential for antitubercular activity. The obtained information is useful for operating as a positive reinforcement of the tendency to use antitubercular properties as a guideline for the drug design.

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Conflict of interest:

There is no any conflict of interest.

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